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Deliverable 4.2

Stakeholder Engagement and Outreach Plan

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Authors: Main: Ramaz Kvatadze (GRENA) Carmela Asero (EFIS). Contributors: Matias Barberis (EFIS), Frederik Tilman (GFZ), Chris Atherton (GEANT), Kurosh Bozorgebrahimi (SIKT)

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Abstract

This deliverable describes the Stakeholder Engagement and Outreach Plan for the SUBMarine cabLEs for ReSearch and Exploration (SUBMERSE) project. The deliverable is related to Task 4.2 Stakeholder Engagement and Outreach and provides the objective and approach for identifying and engaging with the stakeholders relevant for the purpose of the project. The report provides an overview of the various groups of stakeholders and how they will be engaged with various work packages of the project.

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Executive Summary

The SUBMERSE project aims to prepare and deploy a standardised research instrument leveraging State of Polarisation (SoP) and Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) techniques in several geographically diverse locations. It has the ambition to release the measurements with existing telecommunication fibres, which will minimise operational and maintenance costs and provide sustainability of the established systems. The data obtained with deployed research infrastructure will provide important information in various fields of Earth science, such as cetology and abiotic and biotic marine interactions, oceanography, seismology, volcanology. Potential societal relevant applications include environmental hazard monitoring as well as earthquake and tsunami early warning.

Hence it is essential to establish a consistent and effective approach to support engagement and outreach of diverse stakeholder groups that will be interested in project outcomes and in data generated by the research instruments. The objectives, structure and available resources of the SUBMERSE project were carefully considered during the development of the stakeholder engagement and outreach plan.

The aim of the stakeholder engagement and outreach plan is to contribute to the implementation of project objectives and maximise its visibility among stakeholders in a coordinated way. Taking into account the wide range of potential stakeholders, Task 4.2 Stakeholder Engagement and Outreach will work in close cooperation with all four work packages of the project to develop, agree and implement this plan. For this purpose, national coordinators for each of the instrument sites were allocated. The role of the national coordinator is to liaise with the various stakeholders from the technical, operational and user groups side with the aim to progress the development of installation at each site. Currently there are 4 national coordinator groups representing Greece, Norway, Portugal and Brazil. In addition, the process of defining person responsible for stakeholder engagement activities for each WP is in progress. Consistent work of all four tasks of WP4 Communication, Exploitation and Impact is essential for the successful implementation of this plan.

The following activities are proposed for identifying and engaging with stakeholders:

- Identify stakeholders – the individuals and/or organizations who have an interest and provide input to the project, special stakeholder groups will be established for research organizations that are interested in usage of obtained data.
- Stakeholder mapping: identify the role of each stakeholder or organization, what expertise they have and how they can contribute to the success and sustainability of the project.
- Establish and plan the engagement activity (e.g. type, frequency) appropriate to each stakeholder group.
- Execute adopted engagement plan.

- Review the engagement activity to evaluate success, analyse lessons learned and revise the plan for further improvement.

These steps are explained in more details in the following chapters.

During identifying, contacting and engaging with the stakeholders' the project will comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) on the protection of collection and processing of the personal data.

This report provides an overview of stakeholder groups and engagement channels that will be used to meet the needs of stakeholders and to maximize the outcomes of the SUBMERSE project.

1 Introduction

Well-established types of stakeholder groups and effective channels for their engagement are essential for the success and long-term sustainability of the SUBMERSE project. For these reason objectives and work plan of the project presented below are carefully considered:

1. Establish a standardised concept architecture for a new scientific research instrument which integrates State of Polarisation (SoP) and Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) into single telecoms submarine cable systems and disseminate generated data to existing research infrastructures in a scalable way.
2. Deploy a standardised prototype research instrument in at least 3 geographically diverse locations based on the needs expressed by research communities for long-term, consistent, ocean bottom and near shore in-situ monitoring utilising SoP and DAS techniques, calibrated and validated against moorings, temporary ship, deployed ocean bottom and terrestrial sensors, in collaboration with industrial partners.
3. Produce open access datasets at a scale not achieved before, through the integration of technologies not previously combined. Efficient use of data produced will be achieved by down sampling and pre-processing techniques developed in the project, in order to select as much scientific data as possible while keeping storage costs manageable. Pre-processed data will be produced in a machine-readable way and can be processed by machine learning algorithms, allowing the integration into the European data space via the EPOC ERIC and the EOSC, Destination Earth and Copernicus Marine Service programmes.
4. Analyse the capabilities and comingling of the technologies involved and create evidence that research infrastructure can be expanded at reduced cost by utilising existing telecommunication systems, rather than laying dedicated expensive submarine fibre.
5. Develop a knowledge body and understanding of a unique technological deployment in collaboration with research communities, research infrastructures and industry. Such knowledge body will allow an increase in the technological level of the global telecoms industry and the involved research infrastructures. The equipment manufacturers will definitely benefit from the development of scientific market.
6. Establish training and capacity building activities to enhance the collection, interpretation, processing and reuse of the data generated by the research instruments, targeting project internal staff and all potential stakeholders interested in integrating the data generated into their scientific workflows, as well as the wider general public.

The deliverable describes the stakeholder engagement and outreach plan consisting of description Task 4.2 objectives including cooperation with other work packages of the project (Section 2), identification and analyses of stakeholder groups (Section 3), definition of relevant engagement channels (Section 4), GDPR compliance during collecting personal data (Section 5) and monitoring and evaluation of conducted engagement activities (Section 6). The final section 7 draws some conclusions.

The report aims to provide guidance in stakeholder mapping to all work packages and tasks of the project. This will lead to more efficient and targeted engagement strategy and will

provide high quality contributions from the stakeholders. During preparation of this report stakeholder engagement plan and used methodology in several projects co-funded by European Union ([GEANT](#) GN4-3 and GN5-1, [NI4OS-Europe](#), [EOSC FUTURE](#)<https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/>,<https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/> [TWIND](#), [RE-SOURCING](#), etc.) were analyzed and considered.

2 Stakeholder Engagement and Outreach

The main goal of the Task 4.2 Stakeholder Engagement and Outreach is to identify and approach relevant stakeholders, make them aware of the outcomes of the project and promote adoption of the related data services. For this reason, the following types of the stakeholders are considered for cooperation: research organizations working in the geosciences and marine sciences as well as in other related scientific fields such as climate, seismology etc., submarine cable system service provider companies, companies that could utilise produced data and national research and education networks providing connectivity to the research communities. The objectives of stakeholder engagement includes:

- Identifying stakeholders and developing an internal marketing and communication guidelines to address them in a coordinated way together with Task 4.1.
- Developing and maintaining relationships with research organizations which might be interested in obtained data analysis by providing detailed information about gathered data structure and consultancy concerning usage of the data.
- Assessment and analysis of the needs of geosciences and marine sciences communities in data obtained by the project.
- Delivering information and insights on current status of the project to the submarine cable system service provider companies aiming to cooperate with them in the expansion of project activities in other regions of the world.
- Regularly disseminate information about project results with NRENs and academic communities around the world.
- Running a peer-reviewed competition across contacted communities to access raw datasets produced by the research instruments (approximately month 30 of the project). This will be achieved in coordination with Task 3.4 Accessibility and Community Use participants.
- Promote project results beyond the immediate communities concerned and expand outreach to wider audience such as European Open Science Cloud and European Data Infrastructure initiatives, research infrastructures, public bodies, etc.
- Presentations and knowledge-sharing at the stakeholder conferences and workshops, development of communication material, participation in dissemination events.
- Working towards the engagement of stakeholders in workshops organized by the Task 3.4 to promote generated datasets as well as in capacity building trainings on data access of Task 4.3 Capacity Building and Training.

The figure below presents the structure of the work in the project and how various work packages interact with each other. Task 4.2 is in close cooperation with all work packages to

identify and map stakeholders and establish suitable communication channels for each group of stakeholders that will maximise visibility and outcomes of the project.

Figure 2.1 Structure of work packages in SUBMERSE

3 Stakeholder Identification

Stakeholder identification and mapping is an important step in understanding who the stakeholders are, what interest and expertise do they have and how they can contribute to the project. The objective of this activity is to provide that stakeholders are continuously up to date with the SUBMERSE project progress. Another important objective is supporting the relevant research community to use the data generated by the research instruments in their scientific work. Equally important is the need to communicate with submarine cable system service providers regarding the importance of implementation of this technology in other parts of the world. The initial analysis stakeholder landscape was carried out during proposal preparation. The project has diverse range of stakeholders, including:

- Project Advisory Board, Project Management, Work Package Leaders, Task Leaders and project participants
- Project partner organizations
- Research/user communities:
 - National research communities associated with research instrument sites in Norway, Portugal and Greece
 - Seismology (data distribution through ORFEUS-EIDA)

- Oceanography (data distribution through the in-situ component of the Copernicus Marine Service)
- Marine biology
- Relevant networks, organisations:
 - Distributed Acoustic Sensing Research Coordination Network DAS RCN
 - Incorporated Research Institutions for Seismology IRIS
 - JTF SMART Cables
- Destination Earth
- Technology side:
 - DAS developers
 - SOP developers
 - Submarine cable system operators
 - Submarine cable system developers
 - National Research and Education Networks (NRENs)
- Policy side:
 - Submarine cable protection committee
 - European Defense Agency
 - Group on Earth Observations (GEO)
 - International Seabed Authority
 - UNESCO – International Oceanographic Commission
- EU institutions, including European Commission
- EU Research Infrastructures and related initiatives
 - European Plate Observing System (EPOS-ERIC)
 - European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)
 - LifeWatch ERIC European Research Infrastructure Consortium
 - Related EU projects (eg. GeoINQUIRE)
- e-Infrastructure Reflection Group e-IRG
- Relevant national agencies e.g. earthquake monitoring agencies, tsunami warning centres, etc.
- General public

4 Engagement channels and Content of Communications

In order to reach various stakeholder groups, the channels for engagement are wide-ranging. The selection of channels and content of communication depends on the stakeholder type and the nature and aim of the engagement (e.g. strategic, technical, communication).

- **Publications in high-quality peer-reviewed research journals** like IEEE Communications, CODATA Data Science Journal, and others.
- **Project website** <https://submerse.eu/> The project has published an initial website which will expand and develop to incorporate new content and results as the project progresses. The website will act as a key element in the communications and dissemination strategy of the project. The website itself will be updated on a regular basis, and all project participants will contribute with material to the website which will be managed and maintained by Task 4.1.
- **Project partner websites and newsletters**
 - Websites of partners, newsletters and magazines will be utilised to help expand the appropriate content dissemination at national/regional level.
 - WP4 is investigating the option of a subscriber newsletter.
- **Targeted mailings** via periodic newsletters
- **Social media**
 - Twitter/X – the project has a Twitter/X presence <https://twitter.com/SUBMERSEproject>, but given the uncertainty surrounding the platform, WP4 investigated other suitable social media platforms.
 - After the discussions within the project management it was agreed that the main social media platform will be LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/submerse-project/>, which offers great potential for professional networking and would help to expand the project audience
- **EC channels** – e.g. [CORDIS](#), [Horizon Results Booster](#)
- **Events:**
 - **Project workshops and trainings:** in accordance with the Task 4.3 training programme will address knowledge and skills development on:
 1. collection, classification and interpretation of the marine acoustic, geoseismic and oceanographic raw data (M6-18);
 2. integration of the codified data into standardized and harmonized datasets and associated metadata (M18-24);
 3. analytical processing of datasets into scientific workflows for biodiversity and ecosystems research, e.g., biodiversity mapping, impact on biodiversity, etc. (M25-36).
 - **Partner workshops and conferences:** WP4 created an internal document collecting input by project partners to identify and track participation to relevant workshops and conferences that will be used to present project results. For example, GEANT TNC research and education networking conference and workshops, NORDUNET conference and workshops, etc.

- **Research community events** preliminary list of suitable conferences were established and presented below. This list will be regularly updated in cooperation with other work packages:
 - Seismology community: annual or otherwise regular meetings of: International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics IUGG; European Geosciences Union EGU; American Geophysical Union AGU; European Seismological Commission ESC and other events with a narrower regional or domain focus
 - Technology community: Distributed Acoustic Sensing Research Coordination Network DAS RCN; Incorporated Research Institutions for Seismology IRIS; JTF SMART Cables
 - Marine community: European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly
 - Geoscience: Living Planet Symposium
 - Policymakers: GEO Plenary

The table below represents communication channels for reaching various target groups.

	Publications in research journals	Project website	Partner websites and newsletters	Targeted mailings	Social media	EC channels	Events
Project participants	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Partner organizations	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Research/user communities	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Technology side	+	+		+	+	+	+
Policy side		+			+	+	
EU institutions		+	+	+	+		+
EU Research Infrastructures	+	+	+	+	+	+	
e-IRG		+	+	+			+

Relevant national agencies	+	+	+	+	+		
General public		+	+		+		

Table 1 Usage of various communication channels for targeted audiences

Content should – wherever possible – be created in such a way that it can be easily used or adapted by project partners. This drives engagement across the project and provides partners are in a position to publish the content on their own channels, potentially increasing reach. WP4 will engage and collaborate with all work packages to identify content opportunities and work with relevant participants to create and publish this content in order to support the project objectives.

As provided in Deliverable D.1 Project Communication Strategy and Plan developed content can be grouped into two types: ‘functional’ and ‘impactful’ (twin-track approach):

- Functional – an informational approach that addresses the ‘what?’ – highlighting facts, features and necessary information. For example, information on the technology, the equipment and the research instrument sites that will be of interest to partners, national communities associated with these sites and industrial communities such as cable system providers, etc. The most suitable channels for these audiences will include websites, media/publications, virtual and in-presence trainings relevant to those audiences and specific conferences or town halls or similar formats attached to major community conferences.
- Impactful – an approach that explains the ‘why?’ – highlighting the benefits to audiences such as funders and scientific communities, and including articles, interviews, success stories, videos, graphics, etc. The most suitable channels for type of stakeholders include websites, social media, and articles, as well as selected conferences. For example, articles on how the project is benefiting a particular research community or the value of the generated data in several scientific disciplines. Correctly established and developed content and use of appropriate channels are important for the successful implementation of project objectives.

Finally, it should be mentioned that the SUBMERSE project has already organized a dedicated session at the largest research and education networking conference TNC23 held on 5-9 June 2023 in Tirana (see Appendix 1 for the session programme). Also presentations of the project were given at the 28th General Assembly of the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics (IUGG), held on 11-20 July 2023 in Berlin (see abstract of presentation in Appendix 2), and at the NORDUnet Community Workshop in September 2023. In addition, NORDUnet has produced a video about SUBMERSE for TNC23

<https://nordunet.box.com/s/gttvw1r3jhfyl03nfuewhk9ns3sswfof>

5 GDPR Compliance

While identifying, contacting and engaging with stakeholders SUBMERSE project will comply with the GDPR on the protection of natural persons with regard to collection and processing of the personal data. The following requirements will be considered:

- When contacting the stakeholders, they will be asked to provide only a minimum of personal data, i.e. name, affiliation, role in the organization, country and contact data.
- No sensitive data will be collected from the stakeholders.
- The personal data collected from the stakeholders will not be publicly available. The personal data will not be shared with third parties and will only be used for the purpose of project's interaction with stakeholders. No contact data will be shared without consent.
- No secondary use of personal data will be performed. In order to determine an efficient communication strategy with the identified stakeholders and to cluster them into groups only information about their role in the organization will be used.
- The stakeholders will be approached in their professional capacity in the context of the SUBMERSE project only.
- The stakeholders reserve the right to terminate communication with project at any time upon their request.
- Stakeholder contacts will be stored by the project partner in a secure database.
- When inviting the stakeholders to participate in project activities, details about the format and the objective of the activity will be provided in advance, so that they can choose if they want to participate.
- During the SUBMERSE project event registration process, participants will be asked to comply with General Terms and Conditions of Use (GTC) and will be informed about the use of their data.

6 Monitoring and evaluation

Monitoring and evaluation of the stakeholder engagement process is essential to provide for active communication of the diverse groups of stakeholders with the project. The input and feedback received from the stakeholders will be carefully analysed. This will give the possibility to measure the effectiveness of the engagement activity and if needed establish further action items, revisit the original plans and implement new steps.

Dissemination of project results and support of research groups interested in utilizing the data generated by the installed research instruments will be crucial for future sustainability.

For this reason dedicated activities are planned in the project.

An important part of Task 3.4 is the interaction with active and potential users to understand academic, research, societal and industrial needs. Relevant workshops will thus be organised to promote these new datasets, improve data discovery and interoperability and adjust services and archival strategies based on user requirements. In connection with the workshops, training sessions will be offered on data access and embedding the data in research workflows, organised by Task 4.3, and stakeholders will be engaged by Task 4.2. The training activities will address knowledge and skills development including metadata format, persistent identifiers, etc. The aim of the project is to produce FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) research data. Trainings and capacity building activities will be delivered mostly online (e.g., webinars, tutorials, use cases and e-learning courses), according to a comprehensive plan, well-established learning objectives and methodological criteria in order to maximise knowledge sharing and training impact.

For the purpose of evaluation of conducted stakeholder engagement activities the following information will be collected:

- Number of stakeholders who have participated in each training activities that will address knowledge and skills development.
- Conducted webinars, developed tutorials and e-learning courses.
- Titles and types of presentations at the international and national conferences, symposia, workshops and seminars.
- Peer-reviewed publications of project participants
- Other publications
- Media publications.
- List of research organizations using data generated by the installed research instruments.

Together with above mentioned information project relevant key performance indicators (KPIs) will be used for regular analyses.

Work Package (WP)	Major KPIs and brief description
WP4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → KPI4.1: Presentations and knowledge-sharing at 6 stakeholder conferences and/or workshops at M36 → KPI4.2: Unique website visitors: ≥1000 at PM18 and ≥2500 at M36 → KPI4.3: Website page views monthly: ≥5000 at M18; ≥15000 at M36 → KPI4.4: Number of training courses by the end of the projects: ≥ 3 → KPI4.5: Number of subscribers to the newsletter: ≥300 at M18; ≥1000 at M36 → KPI4.6 : Twitter followers ≥500 at M18; ≥1500 at M36 → KPI4.7 : project videos (at least 2) targeting views ≥1000 at M18; ≥5000 at M36

Based on this evaluation, if required, additional steps to intensify the stakeholder engagement process will be established and implemented. For the successful implementation of stakeholder engagement and outreach activities and communicate the findings with the stakeholders close collaboration between all work packages is necessary.

Obtained information will be published on the project SharePoint space and updated as the project progresses. This information will be reviewed by the Project Management Board PMB every six months.

7 Conclusions

This document provides an outline of the stakeholder engagement process that is an important element for the successful implementation of the SUBMERSE project. The stakeholder engagement activities will be strongly supported and are naturally accompanied by the dissemination activities Task 4.1 Communication and Dissemination to provide for a systematic outreach and efficient messaging to the target groups. Hence there is a mutual dependency between the work of Task 4.1 and the stakeholder engagement Task 4.2.

At the initial stage a detailed identification of stakeholder groups was performed. The wide range of stakeholder groups external to the project were established and are presented in this report. The diverse nature of stakeholder groups and their interests require close collaboration and coordination of all work packages.

The report provides a detailed overview of engagement channels and the content of communication that will be used in the project. Also, complying with the GDPR with regard to collection and processing of the personal data will be provided. .

The two strategic goals of the project are following:

1. To provide for sustainability of developed and installed research instruments beyond the SUBMERSE project lifetime. This will be achieved by the targeted dissemination of project findings and results to the potential funding organizations, e.g. European Commission, EU Research Infrastructures, national and local governments, relevant research institutions, National Research and Education Networks, submarine cable system operators, etc.
2. To reach effective usage of datasets generated by the established infrastructure in various scientific disciplines, such as seismology, oceanography, marine biology, DAS and SOP development, etc. The collected data will follow FAIR principles that support its wide utilization. The project acknowledges that due to both limitations of storage capacity and due to potential security implications of acquired data, not all acquired data will be releasable under FAIR principles, but FAIR data distribution might represent subsets in (time, space, frequency, wavenumber)-domains. The aim is to make as much data available under FAIR principles as possible.

Finally, stakeholder engagement is an ongoing activity of the project and aims to build a sustainable two-way communication and collaboration with the most relevant experts and institutions. Regular monitoring and evaluation of the engaging activities will be performed in order to explore areas for improvements.

References

CORDIS	https://cordis.europa.eu/
EOSC FUTURE	https://eoscfuture.eu/
GEANT	https://geant.org/
NI4OS-Europe	https://ni4os.eu/
RE-SOURCING	https://re-sourcing.eu/
SUBMERSE	https://submerse.eu/
TWIND	https://twindproject.eu/

Glossary

AGU	American Geophysical Union
DAS RCN	Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) Research Coordination Network
D	Deliverable
DAS	Distributed Acoustic Sensing
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EGU	European Geosciences Union
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPOS	European Plate Observing System
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESC	European Seismological Commission
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reuse
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IRIS	Incorporated Research Institutions for Seismology
IUGG	The International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics
JTF	JTF SMART Cables
NREN	National Research and Education Network
SOP	State of Polarisation
SUBMERSE	SUBMarine cableS for ReSearch and Exploration Definition
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Appendix 1

Research and education networking conference TNC23 held on 5-9 June 2023 in Tirana

Session: SENSEational Networking

Chair: Chris Atherton (GÉANT)

What can we learn about our planet using submarine optical cables

In last decades the massive use of telecommunications has driven the need to lay millions of kilometers of optical fiber cables across the entire planet, particularly our oceans. Recent developments in optical fiber sensing have revealed the possibility to transform all these cables into powerful geophysical sensing arrays, capable of measuring in a position-resolved way variables such as strain and temperature with high sensitivity and across tens of kilometers of distance. In this talk I will review the key technological aspects behind these systems with particular focus in the achievable performances in this applications needs.

Speaker: Sonia Martin-Lopez (Universidad de Alcala)

Recent advances in earthquake monitoring in Albania

The Seismology Department is a basic research unit at the Institute of Geosciences (IGEO), part of Polytechnic University of Tirana (UPT), Albania, which has the task: to conduct scientific and applied studies in the field of seismology; to administer the Albanian Seismological Network (ASN), as the only national infrastructure for earthquake monitoring and development of scientific research in the field of seismology; and finally to continuously monitor 24/7 seismic activity in Albania and around it, as well as to inform in event of earthquakes the relevant governmental units and the public. The November 26, 2019 (Mw6.4) earthquake in Albania evidenced many problems related with the prompt reaction and processing capabilities of ASN. The sparse network influenced the detection and the quality of the solutions. Hence, as a result of a close collaboration with Karlsruhe Institute of Technology and ADRIARRAY Team, our country counts nowadays 409 temporary monitoring seismic sensors targeting a more accurate regional and local seismicity analysis and body wave tomography. Alongside the RESEAL Project, 10 new permanent seismic stations have been constructed and equipped with the necessary infrastructure, ready to transmit seismic records in the coming months.

However, the western part of the country, being the most urbanized area with significant seismic hazard levels, prone to large earthquakes in the past, is not properly monitored from the seaside. Fiber-optic sensing techniques, including distributed acoustic sensing, can offer a powerful way of monitoring this environment. With improved software infrastructures and data processing techniques, this solution could intensely impact observational seismology.

Speaker: Anila Xhahysa (Albanian Institute of Geosciences)

Fiberoptic sensing in the Arctic - research, technology and opportunities

Recent years have shown a rapid development utilizing acousting sensing on already deployed fiber optic cables. This presentation will go through experiments and results obtained so far in the far north arctic, showing a variety of use cases including whale and

wessel tracking, earthquake and distant storms registration etc. We will also take a brief look into new sensing techniques and and how to combine acoustic sensing with conventional optical network roll-out.

Speakers: Kurosh Bozorgebrahimi (Sikt), Olaf Schjelderup (Sikt)

Appendix 2

The 28th IUGG General Assembly (IUGG2023) held on 11-20 July 2023 at the CityCube in Berlin, Germany.

Session: S05a - Advances in Earthquake and Explosion Monitoring Using Distributed Acoustic Sensing

Abstract

Towards continuous monitoring in the oceans with submarine telecommunications cables using fibre optic technique: the SUBMERSE project

Chris Atherton GÉANT Vereniging (Association)

Ramaz Kvatadze Georgian Research and Educational Networking Association GRENA

Frederik Tilmann GFZ German Research Center for Geosciences

In last few years, a number of technologies to use fibre optic cables as sensing devices have been established, among them Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) and State-of-Polarisation (SoP). The potential of these technologies for monitoring a range of Earth System parameters in submarine cables has been demonstrated through several pilot experiments. Yet, continuous access to sub-marine optical fibre scientific data has currently not been achieved anywhere, neither has full integration of the various techniques.

The SUBMERSE project links Research and Education Networks (NRENs), universities, research institutes and industry to establish multi-method monitoring along submarine optical telecommunication cables at several key cable routes branching off from Portugal, Madeira, Svalbard and in the Aegean. Those pilot sites should serve as a blueprint for establishing continuous monitoring services along many more cables.

The project comprises technical developments for integrating DAS and SoP measurements, for establishing differential SoP measurements between repeaters and for operating DAS in 'lit' fibres, i.e., fibres carrying telecommunications traffic. Furthermore, a range of geoscientific and marine biology use cases are included, which seek to establish code/services for monitoring earthquakes, tracking whales, measuring the sea state and other Earth System variables. Effective data management, dissemination and training through community specific services will be addressed in several tasks as they are crucial for the success of this project due to the large size of data, sensitivity of a subset of the recordings and current lack of established community standards. SUBMERSE clearly commits to open and FAIR data exchange.